

Invitation to participate in the research "Exploring Computer Science Education for Non-Tech Experts in Brazilian context"

1 – Title:

Exploring Computer Science Education for Non-Tech Experts in Brazilian context

2 – Invitation:

It is important that you understand the motivations of the study before your participation. Take as much time as you need to read the information below. If anything is unclear or if you need more information, please feel free to send questions to any of the emails at the end of this document.

3 - What is the objective of the study?

There is a growing interest in learning programming. Although there are many resources available to facilitate learning, Computer Science is a broad field consisting of various distinct topics. Consequently, each student may have different objectives, requiring a personalized educational approach. Thus, this study aims to identify the different profiles of non-technical students who are learning to program, as well as their respective difficulties. Furthermore, it envisions opportunities to enhance computer education for specific groups, thereby contributing to the advancement of Brazilian society.

4 - Why is this project important?

The study will identify opportunities to improve computer education for non-technical individuals, with the aim of meeting the specific learning needs and objectives of students.

5 - Do I have to participate?

Your participation is important to us, but it is up to you to decide if you feel comfortable participating in the research. If your answer is positive, you will fill out the questionnaire about sociodemographic data and knowledge about programming. Additionally, you are free to change your decision at any time and withdraw from participating in this research, without needing to provide justifications and without any consequences.

6 - What will happen to me if I participate? What do I have to do?

Once you authorize your participation, you will fill out this questionnaire. At the end, you will submit your response, which will be subsequently coded in order to maintain complete confidentiality of the information provided.

7 - Will my participation in this study be kept confidential?

Yes. The research is completely anonymous, so you do not need to identify yourself at any time. The collected information will be kept secure, coded, and identification can only

be performed by personnel directly involved with the project. If the material is used for scientific publication or teaching activities, names that could identify the respondent will not be used.

8 - Financial Remuneration:

No financial incentive or reward is provided for your participation in this research. You will incur no expenses by participating in the research.

9 - How long will it take to complete this survey?

We estimate approximately 15 minutes.

10 - Contact for additional information:

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

1. Do you agree to participate in the research? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

I am 18+ years old and I voluntarily agree to participate, understanding that I may withdraw my consent at any time, before or during the study, without penalty or prejudice."

I do not agree to participate in the study.

Sociodemographic Profile

2. Gender *

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Female

Male

Outro: _____

3. Ethnicity *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Asian

White

Brazillian Native

Black

Parda

I prefer not to answer

Outro: _____

4. Age Range *

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18 - 25

25 - 35

35+

I prefer not to answer

5. Brazilian state (current) *

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AC

AL

AP

AM

BA

CE

DF

ES

GO

MA

MT

MS

MG

PA

PB

PR

PE

PI

RJ

RN

RS

RO

RR

SC

SP

SE

TO

6. Assinale a situação abaixo que melhor descreve seu caso: *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I do not work and my expenses are funded by my family.
- I work and receive financial assistance from my family.
- I work to pay my expenses.
- I work and contribute to my family's financial assistance.
- I work and am the person responsible for my family's expenses

7. What is your monthly per capita family income? (To calculate, add up the monthly income of all household members and divide by the number of residents) *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Up to 2 minimum wages
- From 2 to 4 minimum wages
- From 4 to 7 minimum wages
- More than 7 minimum wages

Questions about CS-Related knowledge

8. What is your educational background and field of study? *

Format: "Current Level of Education" eg.: "Technical Nursing Course"

Note: If you do not have a specialization, you can indicate your last qualification. eg.: "Completed High School" eg.: "Incomplete Bachelor's Degree in Administration"

9. Why did you decide to learn programming? *

10. When did you start learning programming? *

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- Less than 2 weeks ago.
- Less than a month.
- Six months ago.
- A year ago.
- More than a year.
- More than two years.
- I don't remember.

11. Did you have any prior knowledge? If yes, from where? *

12. What knowledge/technologies were your focus of learning? *

13. How are you learning this skill? *

14. Is there any initiative or project you are working on as a result of your learning? *

15. What was the biggest challenge you faced during the learning process? *

16. How do you plan to use this knowledge in your career? *

17. How does your original academic background relate to CS-related knowledges? *

18. Would you recommend learning programming to other people in your field of study? Why? *

19. Do you think programming knowledge is important for society as a whole? Why? *

20. Comments

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